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Origin of Political Terminology in Arabic Language and Modern Influences on Political Terminology

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Abstract: *This article is devoted to the study of the formation and semantic features of political terminology in the Arabic language. Today, the range of political vocabulary and terminology in the Arab world is very rich, and the development of the political lexicon has increased significantly, especially in recent centuries. The article analyzes the ways in which political terms are formed in the Arabic language, including how they are formed through morphological and syntactic processes, their characteristics, and what semantic loadings they have in social and cultural contexts. In addition, the article analyzes the historical and modern political processes of the Arabic language. The changes and developments experienced in the secret, international political realities and the influence of other languages such as English in the creation of new terms are also studied.*

Key words: *Political terminology, Semantic features, Morphology, Borrow words, Globalization, Metaphors.*

Arabic has a long and rich history and is one of the most widely spoken languages in the world. His political lexicon is very complex and multi-layered, and is inextricably linked with historical processes, cultural exchanges and modern social changes. Political terminology plays an important role not only in public administration and legal issues, but also in everyday life. In today's globalized world, the study of the origin, formation methods and semantic features of political terms in the Arabic language is of great importance, and this process helps to understand the cultural, social and political changes in the Arab world. The main goal of this study is to analyze the data on how political terms are formed in Arabic, what semantic loads they have and how they undergo changes. The relevance of this topic is related to modern political processes, international relations and socio-cultural changes in the Arab world, and by studying these terms, it will be possible to better understand the development of the political speech and lexicon of the Arab world.

A History of Political Terminology in Arabic

Political terminology in the Arabic language has a long history and has undergone significant changes in different periods. The first political terms were formed at the time of the emergence of Islam. For example, terms such as "caliph" (head of the caliphate), "shura" (council), "ummah" (Muslim community) appeared during this period and entered the political lexicon of the Arab world along with the spread of Islam. centuries and during the Ottoman period, as the Arab world was composed of different political structures and states, there were also significant changes in political terminology. During this period, terms such as "sultan" (ruler) and "vezir" (prime minister) that came under the influence of the Turkish language began to be widely used in Arabic. Many new political concepts entered the Arab world through French and English. For example, words such as "republic" (jumhuriyah), "constitution" (dustur) were adopted and adapted to the Arabic language during this period. This process accelerated during the Arab countries' independence movements and national identity.

Formation and morphological features of political terms

The formation of political terms in Arabic is done through different methods. These methods are based on the unique grammatical and morphological features of the Arabic language. Many political terms in Arabic are derived from root words. For example, words such as "hukumah" (government) and "hakim" (judge, ruler) are formed from the word "judgment". Also, when creating new words, word-forming affixes and suffixes are widely used. is used. For example, when forming the word "democracy" (dimuqraṭīyah) from the word "democrat" (dimuqraṭī), the suffix "-iyah" is added. Through such morphological changes, many political concepts are expressed in the Arabic language. In addition, there are political terms borrowed from other languages, especially English and French. These terms are usually adapted to the morphological rules of the Arabic language. For example, the word "constitution" (dustur) is taken from the French language and becomes a new acquisition in Arabic and is accepted as a widely used political term.

The formation of political terms and their morphological features in Arabic is formed through the deep-rooted grammatical structure and rich word formation system of the language. The main attention is paid to the following features:

Root Words and Word Formation: In Arabic, all words come from a specific root, which often consists of three consonants. This root represents the main meaning of the word, and words with different meanings are formed from it. For example, the root "ktb" (kataba) means "to write" and from it various words such as "kitob" (book), "maktab" (school), "kutubkhona" (library) are formed. Political terminology is also often created in this way: from the root "ḥkm" (judgment) words such as "ḥkwī" (government) and "ḥakm" (ruler) are made. different morphological methods are used. These include prefixes (additions added to the beginning of words), suffixes (additions added to the end of words), and infixes (additions added to the middle of words). For example, the Arabic version of the word "democracy" is "ديمقراطية" (ديموقراطية), where the suffix "-iyah" is used to create a new word. These methods make it possible to create new political concepts in Arabic. **Morphological adaptation of proper words:** Political terms from other languages are adapted to Arabic. These acquisitions are adapted to the morphological rules of the Arabic language. For example, "constitution" came from the French word "dstwr". Such adaptations help enrich the new political lexicon in Arabic.

Semantic features of political terms

The semantic characteristics of political terms in Arabic are also different and may change over time. For example, the word "jihad" originally had a religious meaning and meant fighting for the cause of God, but later it began to be used in a political and military sense. Besides, many political terms are the

same. can represent several meanings and concepts. For example, the word "caliph" means a religious leader on the one hand, and a political ruler on the other hand. These types of terms have different connotative and denotative meanings, and their meaning can change depending on the socio-political context. Metaphors and symbolic meanings also play an important role in political terminology in the Arabic language. For example, the word "castle" (castle) is often used as a symbol of the strength and durability of a state or nation. Such metaphorical terms are often used in political discourse to have a strong emotional impact.

The semantic changes of political terms in Arabic and how they acquire meaning in different contexts are also important.

Semantic changes and expansions: The meaning of political terms can change and expand over time. For example, the word "aslam" (Islam) originally had a religious meaning, but now it is often used in a political context. Although the word "Jihad" originally meant a religious movement, it later took on the meaning of a political and military movement. This process shows how terms develop as a result of historical and social changes.

Connotative and denotative meanings: Although political terms in Arabic often have a clear denotative (correct) meaning, they can also have connotative (additional) meanings. For example, although the word "khalifa" (caliph) actually means "vicegerent", in many Muslim countries this word also means a religious and political leader. Thus, terms acquire different meanings depending on the social and political context.

Metaphors and Symbolism: Many political terms in Arabic are expressed through metaphors and symbols. For example, the word "citadel" (citadel) is often used to describe the strength and durability of a state. Such metaphors are used in political discourse to have a strong emotional and symbolic effect.

Contemporary Influences on Political Terminology in Arabic

In today's globalized world, political terminology in the Arabic language is greatly influenced by modern political processes and technological developments. Mass media and the Internet also influence the formation of political terminology in the Arabic language. It is also possible to provide more information about how political terminology in Arabic is evolving with modern processes and technological developments.

Impact of Globalization: The process of globalization has a great influence on political terminology in the Arabic language. For example, the term "globalization" (العولمة, al-'awlamah) entered the Arabic language and became part of the modern political discourse. International political processes, economic and social integration have also enriched the terminology of the Arabic language and introduced new concepts and expressions. **Social networks and technology:** As a result of social networks and technological developments, new political terms and expressions have appeared. For example, after the "Arab Spring" revolutions, phrases like "Facebook revolution" began to be widely used. As these revolutions were organized through social media, these terms became widespread in the Arab world and became part of political discourse.

Media and Language Policy: Media and language policy also significantly influence political terminology in Arabic. For example, in countries such as Egypt or Saudi Arabia, a new political lexicon is introduced, which leads to the formation of a new political discourse. These reforms update political terminology in the Arabic language and help adapt it to modern political realities. Since today's political discussions are often conducted on online platforms, new terms quickly become

popular and spread throughout the Arab world. Through the hashtags used in social networks, new terms and expressions appear, which begin to be widely used in a short time. Also, as a result of the language policy and reforms implemented in some Arab countries, significant changes are taking place in the political lexicon.

Political Terminology and International Relations in Arabic

Political terminology in the Arabic language occupies an important place in the framework of international relations. Political and diplomatic terms are widely used in Arabic in diplomatic relations between the countries of the Arab world and dialogues in international organizations.

Terms in diplomatic communication: political and diplomatic terms are widely used in Arabic in diplomatic communication between Arab countries and international organizations. For example, Arabic terms are used as the main means of communication in the dialogues within the League of Arab States and the Organization of Islamic Cooperation. This further strengthens the importance of the Arabic language at the international level.

Translation and cultural contexts: Many problems arise when translating political terms from Arabic into other languages. For example, some terms in Arabic, especially those with a religious or historical meaning, may not be correctly expressed in other languages. This can lead to misinterpretations and misunderstandings in international relations.

Global impact of Arabic political discourse: Political concepts and terms developed in Arabic are also used in global political discourse. For example, the fact that the term "Arab Spring" has inspired political movements around the world and the use of this phrase in global discourse shows how the Arabic language influences international politics. These terms are important not only in dialogues between countries, but also in international legal documents. There are many problems when translating political terms from Arabic to other languages. Since Arabic terms often do not have exact equivalents, it is difficult to correctly express concepts during the translation process. This can lead to misinterpretations in international relations. In addition, political terminology in the Arabic language has a great influence on international relations. Arab countries use Arabic terms to express their political and diplomatic positions in the international arena, which further increases the importance of the Arabic language at the international level.

Research on the formation and semantic features of the political terminology in Arabic shows several important aspects. First, it allows understanding. Political terms in the Arabic language have been formed and enriched during different periods, starting from the Islamic era, up to the Ottoman Empire and the colonial period. Secondly, the formation of political terms in the Arabic language is often based on the root system and morphological methods of the language. By using word-forming affixes and suffixes to create new political concepts, the Arabic language has adapted to new political realities and adopted new words. Thirdly, political terms in Arabic are semantically rich and diverse. These terms often represent multiple meanings and concepts, which causes their connotative and denotative meanings to change depending on socio-political contexts. Metaphors and symbolic meanings are widely used in Arabic political discourse to convey a strong emotional impact. Fourth, political processes in the modern world, globalization, technological development, and social networks have a great impact on political terminology in Arabic. These influences contribute to the emergence of new political concepts and terms in the Arabic language and their popularization. Finally, political terminology in the Arabic language plays an important role in international relations. Diplomatic relations between Arab countries and dialogues in international organizations are conducted through political terms in the Arabic language, which increases the importance of the Arabic language in the international arena.

At the same time, the problems that arise in the process of translating terms from Arabic to other languages can affect the correct understanding and interpretation of international political discourse. In short, the study of the formation and semantic features of political terminology in Arabic is not only a linguistic point of view. in terms of political, cultural and social contexts. These studies allow for a deeper understanding of the political and cultural identity of the Arab world and strengthen the position of the Arabic language in global politics.

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